

A Comparative Study of Sparse and Dense CNNs under Pixel Threshold-Induced Sparsity for Brain Tumor Classification

Hilary Utaegbulam¹ and Amber Weatherspoon²

¹Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Rochester, Rochester, NY, USA.

²Niles North High School, Skokie, IL USA.

Abstract

We present a comparative study of dense and sparse convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for brain tumor classification in two-dimensional MRI scans. Sparsity is induced at the input by removing pixels with intensity \leq a pixel value threshold τ and passing only the remaining pixel coordinates and their values to sparse CNNs implemented with the Minkowski Engine sparse-tensor framework. We evaluate a small ResNet-style model (“Simple CNN”) and ResNet-101 in both dense and sparse forms on a four-class dataset (glioma, meningioma, pituitary, no-tumor). For the sparse variants, we sweep τ over a broad range and train five independent runs with class-weighted cross-entropy and early stopping. The sparse ResNet-101 achieves the best overall performance at $\tau=0$ with a mean test accuracy of $96.8\% \pm 1.3\%$, while the sparse Simple CNN peaks at $\tau=3$ with $82.7\% \pm 0.6\%$. The confusion matrices show that the no-tumor class is the easiest to classify for all models and that the meningioma class is the most challenging. We also quantify how the retained pixel fraction decreases monotonically with τ . Overall, threshold-induced sparsity matches or improves accuracy relative to dense baselines, especially for the Simple CNN.

This work originated as a mentorship project through the NAACP’s Afro-Academic, Cultural, Technological and Scientific Olympics (ACT-SO) in collaboration with Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory and Argonne National Laboratory.

Keywords: Sparse convolutional neural networks, pixel-intensity thresholding, induced sparsity, brain tumor classification, MRI, ResNet-101, MinkowskiEngine, sparse tensors, sparse cnn, medical image analysis

1 Introduction

Medical imaging classification is critical to the detection and accurate classification of tumors. Deep learning models such as convolutional neural networks have historically been used for medical image classification [1, 2]. These represent dense or conventional convolutional neural (dense CNNs) networks where for 2 dimensional data, all pixels are processed on a dense grid, with fixed-size kernels sliding across the entire image to produce

dense feature maps. Feature maps from conventional CNNs are stored in full dense tensors and convolutions are applied uniformly at every spatial location on a regular grid. Less explored is the applicability of sparse convolutional neural networks (sparse CNNs) for medical image classification [3].

In this paper, we present a comparative study of two dense CNNs, ResNet-101 [4] and a small ResNet-Style CNN and their sparse counterparts. We evaluate whether input sparsity induced by

pixel-intensity threshold cuts can improve classification accuracy on two-dimensional MRI images spanning three tumor classes. We hypothesize that inducing sparsity in this way and processing the resulting inputs with sparse CNNs will improve classification by reducing computation on background regions and allowing models to better focus on features relevant for classification. This work originated as a mentorship project through the NAACP’s Afro-Academic, Cultural, Technological and Scientific Olympics (ACT-SO) in collaboration with Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory and Argonne National Laboratory.

2 ACT-SO

The Afro-Academic, Cultural, Technological, and Scientific Olympics (ACT-SO) is a nationwide program sponsored by the NAACP that encourages high academic and cultural achievement among Black/African-American high school students. ACT-SO is designed primarily as a learning experience, emphasizing enrichment and mentorship. Students collaborate with volunteer mentors to scope, execute, and present year-long projects across STEM, humanities, and the arts. Through this enrichment and mentorship, ACT-SO students gain sustained guidance, research skills, and presentation experience to aid their educational journey.

3 Sparse Convolutions & the Minkowski Engine

3.1 Sparse Convolutions

Dense CNNs operate on a full image lattice where every pixel is processed even if most values are background. This is inefficient for inputs that are naturally sparse such as point clouds or voxelized 3D data. Sparse CNNs reduce computation and memory by evaluating convolutions only at active locations while preserving the inductive bias of locality. Non-active locations, or background, are not passed into the model.

On a dense D -dimensional grid, a standard convolution at location $u \in \mathbb{Z}^D$ aggregates features from a fixed, centered neighborhood:

$$x_u^{\text{out}} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}_D(K)} W_i x_{u+i}^{\text{in}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{V}_D(K)$ is the set of kernel offsets (e.g., a 3×3 stencil in 2D or $3 \times 3 \times 3$ in 3D). The operation is applied uniformly at *every* lattice site [5].

In a sparse convolution, we define sets of active coordinates rather than working with the entire lattice. Let \mathcal{C}_{in} and \mathcal{C}_{out} be the input and output coordinate sets (only locations that actually exist). For an active output site $u \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{out}}$,

$$x_u^{\text{out}} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{N}_D(u, \mathcal{C}_{\text{in}})} W_i x_{u+i}^{\text{in}}, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{N}_D(u, \mathcal{C}_{\text{in}})$ includes only those offsets i for which the neighbor $u+i$ is present in \mathcal{C}_{in} . Sparsity uses the same kernel and local aggregation, but we evaluate it only where data exists [5].

3.2 The Minkowski Engine

The MinkowskiEngine (ME) is a sparse tensor package that represents a sparse tensor by a *coordinate matrix* ($N \times D$) listing active sites and a *feature matrix* ($N \times C$) with features at those sites [5]. A built-in coordinate manager constructs efficient kernel maps that specify, for each layer (kernel size, stride, dilation), which input sites contribute to which output sites. Compute and memory scale with the number of active sites, not the full lattice size.

The coordinate matrix includes the spatial location and batch index for each non-zero pixel, while the feature matrix stores associated pixel values. The general form is:

$$\mathbf{C} = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 & x_1^1 & x_1^2 & \cdots & x_1^D \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ b_N & x_N^1 & x_N^2 & \cdots & x_N^D \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}_1^T \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{f}_N^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{T}[x_i^1, x_i^2, \dots, x_i^D] = \begin{cases} f_i & \text{if } (x_i^1, x_i^2, \dots, x_i^D) \in \mathcal{C} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{T} is the sparse tensor formed by the coordinate matrix C and the feature matrix F .

4 Model Architectures

For this study we use two CNN families ResNet-101 and a smaller ResNet-style model we call

Simple CNN, which we built for this work. We construct dense and sparse versions of SimpleCNN with identical topology. Both begin with a stem 3×3 convolution ($1 \rightarrow 32$) followed by batch normalization (BN) and a ReLU activation. The next stage is a stride-2 residual block: the main path is a 3×3 convolution ($32 \rightarrow 64$) + BN, and the shortcut is a 1×1 projection ($32 \rightarrow 64$) with stride 2 + BN. Their outputs are added and passed through ReLU. A global average pooling (GAP) layer feeds a linear classifier ($64 \rightarrow 4$). The sparse variant replaces all dense layers with MinkowskiEngine counterparts (sparse conv/BN/ReLU/GAP/linear) applied to threshold-selected active pixels. Kernel sizes, channel widths, and strides are matched exactly. Figure 1 shows a diagram of the Simple CNN.

For the dense baseline of ResNet-101, we use `torchvision.models.resnet101` with random initialization (`pretrained=False`). We replace the input to accept one channel images ($1 \rightarrow 64$, 7×7 , stride 2), and set the classifier to four outputs.

The sparse counterpart replaces PyTorch’s dense operations with the Minkowski Engine’s sparse operators. It accepts the threshold-induced sparse inputs (active coordinates and their feature values) as described in Section 5.2. Architecturally, it mirrors the four ResNet stages with Bottleneck depths (3, 4, 23, 3) and projected short-cuts, but every conv/norm/activation is an ME module (ME Convolution, ME Instance/Batch-Norm, ME ReLU/GELU) instead of PyTorch layers. *The stem differs:* the sparse model uses a 3×3 ME conv (stride 2) followed by ME max-pooling (stride 2), rather than the dense 7×7 conv + max-pool. *The head also differs:* after layer 4 the sparse model adds a dropout $\rightarrow 3 \times 3$ ME conv (stride 3) \rightarrow norm \rightarrow GELU block before pooling. *Pooling differs:* the dense model uses global average pooling, while the sparse model uses ME global max pooling, followed by an ME linear classifier. Aside from these operator, stem/head, and pooling changes, the stage counts and downsampling schedule are matched across the two models. This ME sparse version of ResNet-101 is adapted directly from the MinkowskiEngine example implementation [5].

5 Data & Methods

5.1 Datasets

A combination of two datasets is used in this study. We use the publicly released “Cheng” dataset of T1-weighted contrast-enhanced brain MR images, consisting of 3064 axial slices from 233 patients: 708 meningioma, 1426 glioma, and 930 pituitary [6]. These represent the data for the first three categories. The images were acquired at Nanfang Hospital (Guangzhou) and the General Hospital of Tianjin Medical University (Tianjin) between 2005 and 2010, with in-plane resolution 512×512 (pixel size 0.49×0.49 mm²), 6 mm slice thickness and 1 mm gap. The dataset is available via Figshare (DOI: 10.6084/m9.figshare.1512427) [7].

For the no tumor class, we use the Br35H (Brain Tumor Detection) dataset from Kaggle. This dataset has a “no” folder containing 1500 non-tumor MR images that we make use of [8]. It also has a folder of “yes” or positive tumor samples that we do not make use of in this study. Consequently, the no-tumor samples come from a different source than the tumor samples used for training and evaluation. We acknowledge this difference in data source as a potential limitation that should be kept in mind when interpreting results.

5.2 Methods

We use the four-class brain MRI dataset described in Section 5.1 arranged in a class-per-folder directory structure. We randomly sample 70 percent of the datasets for training 30 percent for testing and validation. The training directory is used as the training dataset while the testing directory is split 50/50, randomly into validation and a held-out testing dataset. All images are loaded in grayscale and resized to 224×224 . The images are converted to tensors and normalized with a mean of 0.5 and standard deviation of 0.5. To induce sparsity, we apply an intensity threshold τ on the original 8-bit image values and retain pixel locations where the intensity is $> \tau$. For each image we keep the coordinates of retained pixels and their corresponding scalar intensities as features. This thresholding procedure is applied identically for the training, validation, and test sets for any chosen τ .

Fig. 1 Simple CNN architecture (dense and sparse). Stem 3×3 conv ($1 \rightarrow 32$) \rightarrow BN \rightarrow ReLU; stride-2 residual block with main 3×3 ($32 \rightarrow 64$) + BN and 1×1 projection ($32 \rightarrow 64$), stride 2 + BN; outputs are added \rightarrow ReLU; GAP \rightarrow Linear ($64 \rightarrow 4$). The sparse variant replaces dense ops with MinkowskiEngine (sparse conv/BN/ReLU/GAP/linear) on threshold-selected active pixels. Kernel sizes, channels, and strides are identical.

Fig. 2 Percentage of pixels retained as a function of pixel threshold value τ . Pixel values $\leq \tau$ are removed. The retained fraction decreases monotonically with τ . At $\tau = 0$ roughly 84% of pixels are kept. Higher τ removes more pixels, so the retained percentage decreases with τ .

For the sparse CNNs we sweep through τ values from 0 to 10 in increments of 1 then from 20 to 255 in increments of 10. Training broke at $\tau \approx 130$ because at least one sample no longer had data and resulted in an empty input. We train up to 400 epochs with a batch size of 15, using the Adam optimizer and a learning rate of 1×10^{-3} and cross entropy as the loss function. We address class imbalance by multiplying each class by the per-class weights in the loss function.

$$w_c = \frac{N_{total}}{KN_c}, \quad (5)$$

where w_c is the class weight, N_c is the number of training samples in a class c , K is the number of classes, and N_{total} is the total number of training samples. We run 5 different runs using 5 different random seeds per threshold τ . We use early stopping with a patience of 10 epochs and a 5 epoch warm-up period where early stopping does

not trigger. The best checkpoint is chosen as the epoch with the lowest validation loss.

Once training is complete, we report the training loss and accuracy per epoch and run inference on the model using the held-out test set using the best checkpoint. We then report the test accuracy, a confusion matrix, and a per-class classification report on the test set.

For the dense CNNs we do the same as described above, except there is no thresholding and we pass information through the dense versions of each model as described in Section 4.

6 Results

We evaluated the performance of the dense and sparse Simple CNN and ResNet-101 on a four class brain tumor classification task. The sparse models were trained across a range of pixel value thresholds τ to find the best pixel threshold. We swept

Fig. 3 Example inputs to the dense (far left) and sparse models, with pixel threshold $\tau = 0$ (middle) and $\tau = 20$ (far right). The dense inputs (far left) represent the original form of the MRI scan data. $\tau \in [0, 255]$ but at least 1 scan loses all data after $\approx \tau = 130$ and results in an empty input. Any pixel value $\leq \tau$ is removed from the input. Increasing τ retains fewer pixels, leading to sparser inputs. The two rows are two different MRI image inputs.

Fig. 4 Test accuracy vs. pixel threshold value τ for sparse Simple CNN and sparse ResNet-101. Points show mean over runs with error bars indicating $\pm 1\sigma$. $\tau = 0$ is the best for the sparse ResNet-101 at $96.8 \pm 1.3\%$ while $\tau = 3$ is the best for the sparse Simple CNN at $82.7 \pm 0.6\%$.

Fig. 5 Validation loss vs. pixel threshold value τ for sparse Simple CNN and sparse ResNet-101. Points show mean over runs with error bars indicating $\pm 1\sigma$. $\tau = 0$ is the best for the sparse ResNet-101 at a val loss of 0.0716 ± 0.0229 while $\tau = 2$ is the best for the sparse Simple CNN at a val loss of 0.4418 ± 0.0269 .

from $\tau = 0$ to $\tau = 130$. Figure 4 shows the mean test accuracy as a function of τ , while Figure 5 shows the corresponding mean validation loss.

For the sparse ResNet-101, the best performance occurred at $\tau = 0$, which yielded a mean

test accuracy of $96.8 \pm 1.3\%$. The sparse Simple CNN peaked at $\tau = 3$ with a mean test accuracy $82.7 \pm 0.6\%$.

Figure 2 shows the mean percentage of pixels retained after applying thresholding to remove pixels with pixel value $\leq \tau$. At $\tau = 0$, roughly 84 % of pixels are kept, which primarily removes most of the black non-data backgrounds from image processing. At $\tau = 3$ about 70 % of pixels are retained. Retained percentage decreases with τ . After a rough pixel threshold value of 130, no pixels are left in at least 1 image in the dataset. A visual example of what the dense and sparse models see as input at $\tau = 0$ and $\tau = 20$ is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 6 shows the training and validation loss curves for the two dense models and their sparse counterparts at their respective best τ . These are averaged across all 5 training runs. All four models show good learning with training and validation losses consistently decreasing. The dense models exhibit spikier validation curves and less stable training than the sparse models. However, their validation losses still decrease consistently overall. The ResNet-101 models, both dense and sparse, achieve a significantly lower and more stable validation loss compared to the Simple CNN models.

We evaluated the final classification performance on the held-out test set. A per-class accuracy comparison for all four models is shown in Figure 7. It is averaged across all 5 runs. As expected, the ResNet-101 models significantly outperformed the Simple CNN models across all four classes. The No Tumor class had the highest accuracy across all four models while the Meningioma Tumor class was the most challenging.

We also create a row-normalized confusion matrix via aggregation of all confusion matrices as shown in Figure 8. The Sparse ResNet-101 ($\tau = 0$) model (bottom right) achieved the strongest overall performance. It demonstrated a slight but consistent improvement over the Dense ResNet-101 (bottom left), achieving higher accuracy on the diagonal for all three tumor classes: 0.94 vs 0.84 (Glioma), 0.95 vs 0.91 (Meningioma), and 0.98 vs 0.96 (Pituitary), while matching the near-perfect 1.00 vs 0.99 for the No Tumor class. The Simple CNN models (top row) showed much higher confusion, particularly with the Meningioma Tumor class, which was frequently misclassified as Glioma

Tumor. Still, the Sparse Simple CNN performed slightly better than its dense counterpart.

6.1 Future Work

In this study, we applied an intensity-based thresholding procedure in which pixels with values less than or equal to the specified threshold τ were removed. A more principled alternative is to use an explicit background mask that identifies non-data regions. Because many datasets already provide such masks, leveraging them to exclude background would reduce irrelevant pixels without suppressing informative but low-intensity signal, producing inputs qualitatively similar to the $\tau = 20$ examples in Figure 3 for *all* inputs.

We work in two dimensions for this project. However, the same method can be extended to three dimensions using a three-dimensional dataset like BraTS 2020 [9]. In volumetric MRI, large regions are background (e.g., after skull stripping), so explicit sparsification is often unnecessary. Sparse 3D CNNs are therefore a natural fit and have been used reliably in medical physics other domains, such as particle physics with voxelized data [3, 10].

7 Conclusion

In this study, we conducted a comprehensive comparison of dense and sparse convolutional neural networks for brain tumor classification using 2D MRI scans, with sparsity induced via pixel-intensity thresholding. Input sparsity was induced by removing pixel values below pixel threshold τ and retaining all remaining pixels. Our results show that sparse CNNs implemented in Minkowski Engine match or surpass the performance of their dense counterparts. Sparse ResNet-101 achieved a peak mean test accuracy of $96.8 \pm 1.3\%$ at $\tau = 0$, outperforming the dense variant across all tumor classes. The sparse Simple CNN peaked at $\tau = 3$ with a mean test accuracy $82.7 \pm 0.6\%$. The confusion matrices show that the no tumor class was the easiest while the meningioma class was the most challenging for all models. The sparse variants showed smoother validation behavior and better confusion-matrix diagonals than their dense counterparts, suggesting that removing low-value background regions

Fig. 6 Loss Curves for All Model Types. Training and validation loss curves (mean across 5 runs) for (top left) Dense Simple CNN, (top right) Sparse Simple CNN at $\tau = 3$, (bottom left) Dense ResNet-101, and (bottom right) Sparse ResNet-101 at $\tau = 0$. Solid lines represent training loss, while dashed lines show validation loss. Red dotted vertical lines indicate the average epoch at which early stopping was triggered (patience=10 epochs after 5-epoch warm-up). Sparse models show comparable convergence patterns to their dense counterparts despite operating on reduced feature spaces and reach much lower training and validation losses compared to their dense counterparts.

can stabilize optimization by allowing models to focus on class-relevant features.

This study has important limitations directions for further research. First, it should be noted that the no-tumor class originates from a separate dataset compared to the tumor classes. Although the MRI slices look similar to the tumor classes and are obtained with the same data acquisition device (MRI scans), it is possible that sourcing non-tumor samples from a separate dataset introduces a (potential) domain shift. This should be kept in mind when interpreting results. Second, we use a simple heuristic for intensity thresholding. Future work should incorporate background masks when available to avoid discarding low-intensity but informative structure as described in section 6.1. Finally, this approach naturally generalizes to 3D volumetric MRI scans where sparsity

is greater and intrinsic and where sparse 3D convolutions could yield even more substantial efficiency gains [3, 10].

Our findings support the hypothesis that sparse CNNs are viable alternatives to dense models for medical image classification, particularly in settings where background dominates the field

Fig. 7 Classification accuracy (mean $\pm 1\sigma$ across 5 runs) for each tumor class, grouped by model architecture. Dense models are compared against their sparse counterparts with the best performing pixel threshold value τ (Simple CNN at $\tau = 3$, ResNet-101 at $\tau = 0$). Error bars represent one standard deviation across independent training runs. All models achieve highest accuracy on the no-tumor class. Glioma and pituitary tumors show moderately high accuracy across all models. Meningioma tumors present the greatest classification challenge, though differences between dense and sparse variants remain within error margins.

of view or where resources are constrained and efficiency is a priority.

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Fig. 8 Row-normalized confusion matrices (averaged across 5 runs) for (top left) Dense Simple CNN, (top right) Sparse Simple CNN at $\tau = 3$, (bottom left) Dense ResNet-101, and (bottom right) Sparse ResNet-101 at $\tau = 0$. Each cell shows the proportion of true class samples (rows) assigned to predicted classes (columns). Values near 1.0 (darker red) along the diagonal indicate correct classifications, while off-diagonal values show misclassification patterns. All models achieve strong diagonal structure. Meningioma tumors show the highest confusion rates across models, occasionally misclassified as gliomas or pituitary tumors. No-tumor cases are classified with near-perfect accuracy by all models.

References

- [1] Mienye, I.D., Swart, T.G., Obaido, G., Jordan, M., Ilono, P.: Deep Convolutional Neural Networks in Medical Image Analysis: A Review. *Information* **16**(3), 195 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.3390/info16030195>
- [2] Xie, Y., Zaccagna, F., Rundo, L., Testa, C., Agati, R., Lodi, R., Manners, D.N., Tonon, C.: Convolutional Neural Network Techniques for Brain Tumor Classification (from 2015 to 2022): Review, Challenges, and Future Perspectives. *Diagnostics (Basel)* **12**(8), 1850 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics12081850>
- [3] Li, J., Gsaxner, C., Pepe, A., Schmalstieg, D., Kleesiek, J., Egger, J.: Sparse convolutional neural networks for medical image analysis (2022) <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.19137518.v2>
- [4] He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., Sun, J.: Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pp. 770–778 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2016.90>
- [5] Choy, C., Gwak, J., Savarese, S.: 4D Spatio-Temporal ConvNets: Minkowski Convolutional Neural Networks. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pp. 3075–3084 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2019.00319>
- [6] Cheng, J., Huang, W., Cao, S., Yang, R., Yang, W., Yun, Z., Wang, Z., Feng, Q.: Enhanced performance of brain tumor classification via tumor region augmentation and partition. *PLOS ONE* **10**(10), 0140381 (2015) <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0140381>
- [7] Cheng, J.: Brain Tumor Dataset. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1512427.v5> . T1-weighted contrast-enhanced MRI slices; 3064 images; three tumor classes. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1512427.v5>
- [8] Hamada, A.: Br35H: Brain Tumor Detection 2020. Accessed: 2025-11-09. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/ahmedhamada0/brain-tumor-detection>
- [9] Bakas, S., Reyes, M., Jakab, A., Bauer, S., Rempfler, M., Crimi, A., al.: Identifying the best machine learning algorithms for brain tumor segmentation, progression assessment, and overall survival prediction in the brats challenge. *arXiv preprint* (2018) [arXiv:1811.02629](https://arxiv.org/abs/1811.02629)
- [10] Utaegbulam, H.: LArDRIP: The Liquid Argon TPC Dead Region Inference Project — ML Track Inference Between DUNE's Near Detector Prototype Modules. Slide deck, ND Technical Software Meeting, SLAC, IAIFI Workshop 2025, Menlo Park, CA. <https://indico.slac.stanford.edu/event/9986/>